

Data Governance Plan for Operación Solar

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Executive Summary

In February 2024 Panamá received a donation from the municipality of Fuzhou, China, of solar panels, inverters and lithium batteries. To distribute them, the Panamanian presidency proposed a pilot project that provides on-grid solutions to underprivileged families in remote communities. The project aims to optimize the power supply system, reduce family expenses, and minimize subsidies. After securing supplementary donations, the team required an adequate data management plan.

A data governance plan will be developed for the project to support the organization and provide a reliable framework to manage the data effectively and securely. The plan will govern the project prioritizing high-quality data input, allowing flexibility for the later stages. It will incorporate a degree of flexibility to accommodate the iterative nature of project development, recognizing that adjustments will be necessary as the project evolves.

It was found that current data practices are too informal, non-standardized and inadequate for this magnitude and impact. These practices undermine the public credibility of the organization and permit other inefficiency problems such as poor management, excessive human reviews, late execution, and others. To maximize the efforts of the team, clear data roles must be assigned, and centralized storage that allows participants to develop their work confidently and securely is encouraged.

1. Introduction:

The scope targets 6 communities proposed by the Secretariat of Energy. The members of these communities have a subsidized power supply and are in different provinces, each with about 200 identified beneficiaries. The database management strategy should facilitate target identification, eligibility, resource management, recruitment, security and logistics. By considering methods and tools for harmonization, consistency, accuracy, risk assessment,

documentation and security the plan will be based in a holistic approach. A data governance plan should allow for of the project’s initiatives to be well-structured, strongly funded and sustainable and should foster collaboration among participants.

The aim of this data governance plan is to provide a trustworthy data-driven document that can enhance the project’s activities. The project aims to form a strategic governance plan that allows managers and stakeholders to install photovoltaic systems in remote, low-income households in compliance with all regulations, analyze improved data quality, and lower management costs.

Adequate data quality, documentation standards and metadata are often disregarded or considered too formal in developing countries like Panama. This data governance plan will encourage appropriate methods to archive and document data effectively and securely, therefore, providing a repository of cases that can be retrieved by future participants. Implementing data modelling tools such as QGIS, which requires high-quality geospatial and demographic data, will serve as a platform for visualization, mapping analysis and planning.

2. Methodology:

Data Collection:

The existing data will be collected from various sources, refer to the following table.

n.	Data type	Sources
1	Primary data	Existing paper archives from previous surveys, GIS layers, emails and text messages
2	Secondary data	Plans from ENSA Servicios, and preliminary surveys from Panama Canal Authority (ACP) and ENSA Servicios
3	Open data platforms	Platforms such as OpenStreetMap will serve as a platform for cross-referencing data.

The new data will be collected through MergeMaps, as mentioned in the Framework section. The new table will elaborate.

Data collection methods

Method	Description
Field surveys	Data will be obtained from the beneficiaries personally in their households, through a MerginMaps form.
Stakeholder collaboration	Stakeholders will send preliminary data (maps, client’s IDs, infrastructure locations) and any other data source that can facilitate the operations directly to the project’s administrators.
Open sources	Contrasting or cross-referencing data will be obtained from OpenStreetMaps

Data processing and integration:

1. A centralized data storing unit is encouraged, considering that it is necessary to collaborate in the data processing tasks.
2. Outlying ranges will be incorporated in the original forms to survey the beneficiaries, particularly for the collection of the consumption of the previous month and the average consumption.
3. Duplicated beneficiaries must be merged to prevent errors. The duplicated data should be contrasted mutually with a request to validate the right entry, edit and save it.
4. The units should be standardized, the metric system is in order.

Data integration:

1. Ensure datasets from mentioned sources are compatible and easily comparable by setting parameters for the units, precision, accuracy and completeness.
2. Create a data dictionary that defines key terms, units of measurement, and formats for each type of data (example: power consumption in kWh).
3. Develop a standardized MerginMaps template for data collection and employ the local share tool TransDoc to ensure uniformity across all input sources.
4. Conduct weekly audits to check for inconsistencies in data entries and correct them proactively with the team.
5. Utilize QGIS to combine the data from distinct sources to create a unified system.
6. Utilize Apache Nifi for database Interoperability, it is open source and includes an easy-to-use number of features.

Assumptions:

To be eligible, the users should not reside illegally, not have more than 300 MWh consumption (maximum legal amount for subsidy) and should reside in the designated communities. Not all users have access to smartphones, internet networks or mobile data signals, some of them rely solely on family members for any digital technology usage, even phone calls, so they are highly concerned about the usage of their personal data.

3. Results:

The existing data collected in the field was incomplete and lacks accuracy due to the lack of internet connectivity. The first data collection brigades also lacked a correct planning strategy. With an improved strategy, all the questions formulated for the project will be remembered by the surveyors, the attributes of their responses will be limited consequently with the outlined and the mandatory questions must be answered to submit, also engaging the beneficiaries in the urge for obtaining and communicating this information as well.

Database

The database schema contains three entities. The schema pretends to allow visualization, organization, filtering and verification of criteria. The Beneficiaries entity contains the names of the beneficiaries, and the corresponding information surveyed about them, then it determines if the beneficiary meet eligibility by document completeness. The Community entity contains the surveyed coordinates of the beneficiaries and geometry that will allow the system to determine if the beneficiaries are eligible by location. The Solution entity contains information about the power consumption of each beneficiary, it determines their eligibility by average consumption and retrieving the community where they are located, then determines the corresponding full sun hours and the corresponding number of solar panels and materials.

Database Schema:

Description of the items:

Items	Type	Description
beneficiaryID	PK	Identifies each beneficiary
elegiblelocation	BOOLEAN	Displays if the beneficiary is eligible by their location
geom	POLYGON	Stores information about the database and delimitations
fullname	TEXT	Stores the name of each beneficiary
telephone	INT	Stores telephone numbers
meterID	INT	Stores the number of each meter
NIS/NAC	INT	Stores information about
deedsubmitted	BOOLEAN	Stores condition of the document submission (yes, no)
idsubmitted	BOOLEAN	Stores condition of id submission (yes, no)
location	GEOM	Stores household coordinates (points)
suppliedby	ENUM	Assigns the company that supplies based on location
elegibledocuments	ENUM	Assigns if the beneficiary is eligible by completeness of documents submitted (yes, no, in progress, etc.)
lastconsumed	FLOAT	Stores the power consumption amount of the last monthly bill of each beneficiary
avgconsumed	FLOAT	Stores the average power consumption of each beneficiary
elegibleconsm	BOOLEAN	Assigns eligibility by consumption value (yes, no)
fullsunhours	ENUM	Assigns the full sun hours value to each zone
numberofpanels	INT	Assigns a corresponding number of panels calculated
hubID	PK	Identifies each hub
hubname	TEXT	Designates a name for the hub

buildingtype	ENUM	Designates a type of building (school, church, park)
geom	POINT	Location of each of the hubs

4. Discussion:

Data processing and integration:

A centralized data storing unit is encouraged, considering that it is necessary to collaborate in the data processing tasks.

1. Outlying ranges will be incorporated in the original forms to survey the beneficiaries, particularly for the collection of the consumption of the previous month and the average consumption.
2. The metric systems and units must be standardized, as Panama exhibits a large American influence, with the English system prevailing among older age citizens.
3. Duplicated beneficiaries must be merged to prevent errors. The duplicated data should be contrasted mutually with a request to validate the correct entry, edit it and save it.

For an extended version of the pilot project in this context, a collaborative platform should allow all users to store and backup data in real time. The beneficiaries should be able to visualize the status of their process in an easy manner. The information must be made safe from spyware or cyber-attacks and should limit the beneficiary's access to their information exclusively. An API protocol can be implemented as an access tool to the platform.

In an advanced stage of the project, the database should be a resource designed to storing the new layers of the progress per household and its attributes. It should be able to facilitate the access of all the team members without major difficulties to features and sections that contain valuable information about the results and how they align with the objectives of the project. It should also grant the organization a space to store feedback from beneficiaries and from the organization to future participants.

Limited access to smartphones and internet connectivity among beneficiaries may hinder data collection and engagement efforts. It is essential to encourage and pursue optimal training results, so that the personnel can deliver data accuracy and completeness to the biggest extent possible, since the targeted areas are costly and difficult to reach.

5. Conclusion:

This pilot project aimed at deploying solar energy solutions for underprivileged families in remote communities of Panama represents a significant step towards promoting sustainability and reducing energy expenses for vulnerable populations. Leveraging

geospatial data modelling and robust data governance practices, standards and regulations is essential to ensure the project's success and enhance its overall impact.

Ensuring high data quality is paramount for effective decision-making. Data governance frameworks must prioritize data accuracy, completeness, and consistency to enhance the reliability of the analyses derived from the database. This condition should be procured since the early the latest stages of the project and should be able to sustain further development in the same direction by providing valuable information and examples.

While the establishment of universal standards for energy planning is a noble endeavour, it is crucial to recognize that the effectiveness of these standards hinges on their contextual applicability. Each energy planning project must be tailored to specific local conditions: climate, resource availability, environmental constraints, societal structures, and others.

Informal, insufficient and/or inadequate data collection practices should be discouraged. Beneficiaries often suffer from lack of trust when they are approach with a formular that has inconsistencies, when they have insufficient communication or updates and when they are not told how their PII is handled. With an appropriate management for all the participants, the relationship among all stakeholders will be based on trust.

References

- [1]. MergeMaps Development Team. (2024). MergeMaps (Version 1.0). MergeMaps Inc. Retrieved from <http://mergemaps.com>
- [2]. OpenStreetMap contributors. (2024). OpenStreetMap. Retrieved from <https://www.openstreetmap.org>
- [3]. QGIS Development Team. (2024). QGIS Geographic Information System (Version 3.28). Open-Source Geospatial Foundation Project. Retrieved from <http://qgis.org>
- [4]. Climate Compatible Growth. (2024). *Geospatial data management for energy access modelling and planning*. Open University. Retrieved from <https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/view.php?id=11725>
- [5]. Secretaría Nacional de Energía. (2023). *Secretaría Nacional de Energía*. Retrieved from <https://www.energia.gob.pa/>

